

COMPUTER UPSET, MATRIX NORMS, AND ASYMPTOTIC STABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The asymptotic stability of linear digital systems is examined under conditions of massive transient fault occurrence. It is shown that the usual approach for stability using eigenvalues does not appear suitable for these conditions. A theorem is derived about stability using the norms of the matrix actions on the system.

1. INTRODUCTION

A topic of increasing interest in reliable digital control is the computer upset problem. In a harsh electromagnetic environment, a control computer can be subjected to massive transient faults that can interrupt process control, even if the control computer has redundant elements. During the upset the computer itself can send arbitrary commands to the actuators. This topic presents a host of new problems in the areas of computer design, experiments, and theoretical analysis [1,2].

Previous work in the reliability of redundant digital control systems has assumed that faults arrive one at a time and that the system operated correctly if the number of good components was greater than the number of faulty components. The associated reliability models declared system failure if the number of faulty components was greater than the number of good components. The assumption in the computer upset problem is that most (perhaps all) of the components will simultaneously have a transient fault. In this case, the traditional reliability models declare system failure. That is, these models assume

that the system being controlled has zero tolerance to a faulty control system.

Recent work examines the possibility that system inertia may give the system some tolerance to a control system that is temporarily faulty [2]. If the control computers recover from the upset quickly enough, then the performance of the system may remain acceptable. Current theoretical work attempts to give precise meaning to the ideas of quick-recovery and acceptable-performance. This work combines control theory and reliability theory.

The work described below is a preliminary effort in this area. It considers the basic topic of asymptotic stability for linear systems with discrete control. There are two results. The first result shows that, when considering upsets, the norms of the control matrices are more appropriate than the eigenvalues of the control matrices. The second result is a theorem about norms and asymptotic stability that is useful for designing experiments.

Section two reviews the basic material on asymptotic stability, matrix norms, and eigenvalues in a manner that is appropriate for the contents of this paper. Section three contains an example that indicates the usual eigenvalue condition for stability is not suitable in the presence of control system upsets. Instead of trying to modify the eigenvalue approach, this initial effort develops a stability condition in terms of the matrix norm. Considering matrix norms no longer gives an if-and-only-if condition for stability, but considering the norms permits an easy proof of a very general result for asymptotic stability. This theorem is

presented in section six. Section four discusses the general scenario for the theorem and the motivation for producing this type of theorem. Section five contains an intuitive discussion for the concept of an event having probability one (which is the conclusion of the theorem). Section seven sketches the statistical procedure for using the theorem.

2. ASYMPTOTIC STABILITY

The equations for a system under discrete control can be written as

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k). \quad (1)$$

This equation gives the state vector x of the system at time $k+1$ in terms of the state vector x and the input vector u at time k . The matrix A describes the behavior of the system in the absence of external influences and feedback. The matrix B describes the influence of feedback and the external environment on the system. In this equation, the vector u can contain the elements of the vector x .

Asymptotic stability considers the effect of an initial perturbation on an undisturbed system. If the system is undisturbed (no input from the external environment), then equation (1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= Ax(k) + Bx(k) \\ &= (A+B)x(k) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

because the feedback depends only on the state of the system. The effect of the initial disturbance can be described by the initial vector $x(0)$. This gives

$$x(k) = (A+B)^k x(0). \quad (3)$$

The system is said to be asymptotically stable if

$$0 = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x(k) = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (A+B)^k x(0). \quad (4)$$

The vector $x(0)$ can be thought of as the difference between the initial location and the

desired location. The system is asymptotically stable if this difference is driven to zero.

The norm of a matrix M is denoted by $\|M\|$ and is defined to be the maximum of $|Mv|$ where the absolute value bars indicate the length of Mv and v is a vector of length one. It can be shown that [6]

$$\|(A+B)^k x(0)\| \leq \|A+B\|^k |x(0)| \quad (5)$$

Hence, the system described by equation (3) is asymptotically stable if

$$\|A+B\| < 1. \quad (6)$$

The usual condition for stability is given in terms of eigenvalues. To begin the presentation, the eigenvectors for a matrix M are the vectors v such that

$$Mv = \alpha v \quad (7)$$

where α is a scalar. That is, M just lengthens or shortens the vector v . There is no rotation. The scalar α is an eigenvalue for the matrix M . The standard result is that the system

$$x(k+1) = (A+B)x(k) \quad (8)$$

is asymptotically stable if and only if the matrix $A+B$ has eigenvalues with magnitude less than one. That is, the matrix $A+B$ has "norm less than one" on its eigenvectors.

Clearly, the eigenvalue condition for stability is delicate. It is stated for the case where the matrix $A+B$ remains the same. During an upset, this matrix may change. In particular, the B matrix representing the action of the control system may change. The next section considers such an example.

3. COUNTEREXAMPLE FOR EIGENVALUES

This example considers a rather benign upset condition [2]. There is no clock upset, no noise on the actuator lines, and no berserk computer. For this example the digital controller recognizes that an upset has occurred, and continues to send the previous signals to the actuators. Because signals are sent for varying lengths of time, the system matrix can change. Suppose the system uses state feedback and is described by the equation

$$x(k+1) = A x(k) + B x(k) \quad (9)$$

where A gives the natural response of the system and B gives the feedback response. Suppose the system is periodically perturbed every third cycle. Let the asterisk denote a cycle during which the system is perturbed and the feedback control sends the previous signal. We have

$$\begin{aligned} x(1) &= Ax(0) + Bx(0) = (A+B)x(0) \\ x(2) &= Ax(1) + Bx(1) = (A+B)x(1) \\ * \quad x(3) &= Ax(2) + Bx(2) \\ &= [AA+AB+B] x(2) \\ &= (AA+AB+B)(A+B) x(0) \\ x(4) &= Ax(3)+Bx(3) = (A+B)x(3) \\ x(5) &= Ax(4) + Bx(4) = (A+B)x(4) \\ * \quad x(6) &= Ax(5) + Bx(5) \\ &= [AA+AB+B] x(5) \\ &= (AA+AB+B)(A+B) x(3) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

etc.

This periodicity yields

$$x(3k) = (AA+AB+B)(A+B) x(3k-3) . \quad (11)$$

It is necessary to choose A and B such that both $A+B$ and $AA+AB+B$ are stable, but $(AA+AB+B)(A+B)$ is not stable. Let

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -3 & -3/2 \\ 4 & 3/2 \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 7/2 & 3/2 \\ -3 & -1 \end{bmatrix} . \quad (12)$$

It can be checked that $A+B$ and $AA+AB+B$ are stable, but

$$(AA + AB + B)(A + B) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 3/8 \\ 0 & -1/8 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

is not stable. Hence, the eigenvalue condition does not guarantee stability if the feedback matrix does not remain the same.

4. DISCUSSION FOR A GENERAL RESULT

The theorem in section six is intended to be a guide to performing experiments. This result was developed to satisfy three goals for the experiment. The first goal is directness. The intent is to perform a set of experiments and make immediate conclusions about asymptotic stability. This is to be done without elaborate models. The second goal is generality. The result includes any type of feedback; it includes clock upset and irregular cycle times; it includes noise on the lines being taken as sensor or actuator signals; it includes a berserk computer sending out random commands. The third goal is a simple experiment. The idea is to require measuring only a few parameters. These parameters should be easy to observe.

The scenario for the theorem has two assumptions. The first assumption is that the plant being controlled is subjected to an arbitrary sequence of actions. This assumption includes the default case where there is no upset. It includes the extreme case where the computers are destroyed, the signal lines are cut, and the control surfaces are lost.

The second assumption is a little more restrictive. It considers the norms of the control actions in the arbitrary sequence mentioned above and requires that these norms be independent, identically distributed random variables. The second assumption includes the default case where there are no upsets. The validity of this assumption requires more study, but it seems reasonable if the control system always recovers from an upset. During a single upset the control system may perform a number of actions that

are correlated, but these actions can be combined and considered as a single action. If this is done, then the independence assumption merely requires that the total effect of different upsets be independent.

It can be seen that this scenario satisfies the goal of generality. It also satisfies the goal of simplicity since the only parameter that need be measured is the norm of the control system actions. Section seven discusses the directness.

5. INFINITE SEQUENCES OF EVENTS AND SETS OF PROBABILITY ONE

This section attempts an intuitive discussion of infinite sequences of random events. Consider the simple example of an infinite number of tosses of a fair coin. The infinite sequence of all "heads"

HHHHHHHH ...

and the infinite sequence of all "tails"

TTTTTTTTT ...

both have probability zero. Hence, the set of sequences that contain both an H and a T has probability one, even though this set does not contain all sequences.

To generalize this example to sequences of norms, replace getting an H or T by getting a nonnegative real number. This number is chosen from a probability distribution on the nonnegative real axis.

6. THEOREM ON NORMS AND ASYMPTOTIC STABILITY

The basic idea for reliability in the presence of massive transient failures is that if the control system recovers quickly enough, then the inertia of the system being controlled may prevent a catastrophe. For this initial study, the ideas of system inertia and quick recover are captured by the norms of the matrix actions. A simple example consists of a point mass subjected to a force. A force applied to a large mass produces less acceleration than the same force applied to a

small mass. Hence, system inertia contributes to a small norm. A force applied for a short period of time produces less velocity than the same force applied for a long period of time. Hence, quick recovery contributes to a small norm.

The scenario is that the system being controlled is subjected to an infinite number of arbitrary actions and the norms of these actions are from a probability distribution on the nonnegative real numbers. Obviously, the stability of the system depends on this probability distribution, and it is necessary to get information about this distribution to make conclusions about stability. The result in this section shows that, a conclusion about stability requires knowing only the average value of this distribution.

The condition required by the theorem is sufficient for stability. An example given after the proof of the theorem shows that this condition is not necessary.

Theorem Suppose a system is subjected to a countably infinite number of matrix operations, and the norms of these matrix operations are independent identically distributed random variables. If the expected value of the norms is less than one, then the system is asymptotically stable with probability one.

Proof

Consider the space where each element is an infinite sequence of matrix operations. A typical element of this space has the form

w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots

where w_i is a matrix operation. Since the norm of a product is less than or equal to the product of the norms [6], it is sufficient to prove that

$\|w_1\| \|w_2\| \dots \|w_n\|$

goes to zero as n goes to infinity, except for a set of probability zero.

Suppose the expected value of the norms is $r < 1$.

Choose $\epsilon > 0$.

Since the norms are nonnegative, the Kolmogorov version of the strong law of large numbers applies to their average [5]. That is, there is an integer N and a set of infinite sequences Q with the following property. The probability of Q is bigger than or equal to $1 - \epsilon$, and if

$$w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots$$

is a sequence in Q and $n > N$, then

$$(\|w_1\| + \dots + \|w_n\|) / n < (1+r)/2.$$

The fraction on the right hand side of the inequality is less than one.

Using the result that the geometric mean is less than the arithmetic mean [7] gives

$$\|w_1\| \|w_2\| \dots \|w_n\|$$

is less than or equal to

$$[(\|w_1\| + \dots + \|w_n\|) / n]^n.$$

Since the expression inside the brackets is less than one, the product of the norms for any sequence in the set Q goes to zero as n goes to infinity.

Hence, the set of sequences that are not stable has probability less than ϵ for any $\epsilon > 0$. The theorem is proved.

As an example that the condition in the theorem is sufficient but not necessary, consider the system

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= A x(k) + Bx(k) \\ &= (A+B) x(k) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where

$$A+B = \begin{bmatrix} 1/2 & 0 \\ 1 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

and the system receives no upsets. This system is stable, but the norm of $A+B$ is greater than one.

7. STATISTICS FOR THE EXPERIMENT

This section shows that the theorem in section six permits making conclusions about asymptotic stability directly from an experiment.

To use the result in the previous section subject a system to upset events and compute the mean and standard deviation for the norms of the observed actions. Assume the sample mean is less than 1. Standard statistical methods (using the sample mean, the sample deviation, and the number of trials) permit concluding that the average for the distribution of the norms is less than 1 at some confidence level. Hence, the experiment establishes that the system is asymptotically stable at this confidence level.

8. SUMMARY

This paper is an initial study for the reliability of digital control systems in the presence of massive transient failures. The basic idea is that if the controller recovers quickly enough, then the inertia of the system being controlled may prevent a catastrophe. It is explained how system inertia and quick recovery are captured by the concept of a small norm for the matrix actions on a system. A theorem is derived, under general conditions, that guarantees asymptotic stability with probability one if the average value of the norms is less than unity. An example shows that the usual approach to stability by eigenvalues may not be suitable for systems subjected to massive transient failures.

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